

Monitoring of Fires Caused by War in Ukraine Based on Satellite Data

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Abstract — The focus of this paper is on fire monitoring studies which utilize a variety of satellite data. The study examines various data sources that are used to automatically detect fires at a national level in Ukraine. Existing fire monitoring systems have low spatial resolution, which makes it difficult to detect fires. Therefore, the authors propose an approach that uses both low- and high-resolution satellite data for fire monitoring. The study found that MODIS, Landsat-8,9 and Sentinel-2 satellite data provide reliable information for fire monitoring in Ukraine. These data sources offer a variety of benefits, including high spatial resolution, frequent revisit times, and wide spectral coverage. In order to understand how favorable weather conditions are for the occurrence of fire, the authors used the Fire Potential Index (FPI). The methodology developed in this study provides a promising approach to monitoring fires and understanding the causes of fires, particularly those caused by the war in Ukraine. The authors implemented the fire detection methodology and FPI index assessment in the Google Earth Engine cloud platform, which allowed for efficient processing and analysis of large volumes of data. In conclusion, the paper highlights the importance of using a combination of low- and high-resolution satellite data for fire monitoring.

Keywords — *burnt area, Sentinel-2, Landsat-9, FIRMS, Land Surface Temperature, Fire Potential Index*

I. INTRODUCTION

Environmental deterioration has been observed in recent years as a result of ex-tensive fires. This underscores the significance of detecting and monitoring fires, particularly those occurring in forests, as well as managing their propagation. One effective solution for this issue is through the use of satellite data. Numerous examples of successful fire monitoring techniques have emerged globally, with many relying on AVHRR data from NOAA satellites [1]. Various techniques for monitoring and con-trolling fires, including forest fires, have been developed in recent years due to the environmental degradation caused by large-scale fires. MODIS (aboard TERRA and AQUA satellites) and VIIRS (aboard Suomi NPP and NOAA-20 satellites) are extensively utilized for this purpose [2]-[4]. These satellite systems are seamlessly integrated into monitoring frameworks like the NASA Fire Information for Resource

Management System (FIRMS) [5]-[7]. One of the key advantages offered by MODIS and VIIRS data is their capability to provide real-time monitoring of fire spread, with updates available every 3 hours. Furthermore, this information can be conveniently accessed through various NASA platforms, including WorldView. The MODIS system provides daily fire data with a spatial resolution of one square kilometer, which is useful for detecting hot spots caused by wildfires and other high-temperature events [8]. Nevertheless, it is important to note that the system lacks certainty in affirming that a detected hotspot unequivocally indicates an ongoing fire. Another frequently tapped source is the SPOT-VGT data from the SPOT satellite [9], the disadvantage of these data is low spatial resolution. The launch of Landsat-8,9 satellites significantly expanded the available resources for fire monitoring, making it a valuable source of data on the thermal infrared channel with a spatial resolution of 100 m [10]. Although this data can be scaled down to 30 m, the revisit time of once every eight days may be too long for near-real-time monitoring. This paper [11] presents an algorithm that uses Landsat data to identify burned areas, which can be applied anywhere Landsat and training data are available. This algorithm creates burn probability surfaces by utilizing band values and spectral indices. It employs a combination of pixel-level thresholding and a region-growing process to generate burn classifications. From 1984 to 2015, the BAECV products mapped a greater burned area within the contiguous United States than what the current data in the Global Fire Emissions Database (GFED) and Monitoring Trends in Burn Severity (MTBS) show. The BAECV products document patterns of fire occurrence and its impacts on natural and human systems and are expected to be useful to studies seeking to understand them. The 10-meter spatial resolution of Sentinel-2 data allows for the detection of fires in their early stages and provides updates every five days. The challenge of collecting and storing data for a country's territory over an extended period arises due to the high spatial resolution, necessitating substantial processing resources. The initial findings of a study, presented in article [12], focused on using spectral indices to assess the severity of a forest fire on Madeira Island in August 2016. The results demonstrated a strong correlation between the spectral

indices and the Copernicus Emergency Management Service (EMSR175) analysis, considered as the reference truth. The study suggests that Sentinel-2 could be a valuable tool for monitoring post-fire conditions.

The commencement of the war in Ukraine on February 24, 2022, has prompted an urgent need to ascertain the causes of fires—whether attributable to dry weather conditions [13], [14] or active military operations.

To address this challenge, the proposed solution involves utilizing the Fire Potential Index (FPI) [15], enabling the consideration of weather conditions that could potentially lead to fires. Although the FPI serves as a valuable tool for forecasting the likelihood of fires, its precision in predicting the specific locations of fires is not always guaranteed. Fires may unexpectedly erupt in diverse locations, influenced by various factors such as human activity, lightning strikes, and other natural causes. In the case of Ukraine, the predominant cause of fires is attributed to the ongoing war. Given that military operations are concentrated in the southern and eastern territories of Ukraine, heightened attention will be directed towards monitoring these regions.

II. DATA

A. Satellite data

The analysis draws upon optically corrected Sentinel-2 Level 2A satellite data, which undergoes revisiting every 5 days, to pinpoint fire locations and delineate burned areas. Complementing this, Sen2Cor provides an 11-class Scene Classification (SCL) map as part of the Level-2A surface reflectance product [16]. The information embedded in this map is of notable importance for automated processing techniques. Acting as a dual-purpose cloud and shadow mask, it facilitates the extraction “clear” land pixels from the Sentinel-2 imagery.

In this investigation, the MODIS Fire Information for Resource Management System (FIRMS) [5] serves as the principal data source for detecting hot spots indicative of fire activity. In 2007, the University of Maryland founded the Fire Information for Resource Management System (FIRMS) with funding from NASA's Applied Sciences Program and the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (UN FAO). The primary objective of FIRMS is to provide timely and accurate information on the location of active fires. This initiative specifically caters to the needs of natural resource managers who encounter challenges in accessing satellite-derived fire data.

To validate the generated burn area mask, data from the Landsat-8 and -9 satellites, specifically band B10 (Thermal infrared, resampled from 100m to 30m) [17]. Due to the combined revisit time of Landsat-8 and -9 being 8 days, nearly half as frequent as Sentinel-2, the validation process was selectively conducted. Consequently, the validation process was executed selectively, focusing on cloud-free images and the designated test portion of the territory.

B. Land cover classification

To ascertain the type of land cover impacted by fires, a land cover map is employed. This map was created utilizing cloud technologies and neural network models [18], [19]. To generate the classification map, a combination of data from two satellites was utilized, incorporating SAR data from Sentinel-1 and optical data, which includes 4 bands (red B4, green B3, blue B2, infrared B8) from Sentinel-2.

This optical data was processed at level 2A with a spatial resolution of 10 meters. Satellite data classification was carried out using the multilayer perceptron (MLP) method.

C. Vector data with fires for validation

To validate the map of burned areas in this study, vector data showing the boundaries of fires, which were created on the basis of high spatial resolution data (Planet / WorldView-3), were used. This data set includes fires caused by shelling in southern and eastern Ukraine in 2022. These data collected within Horizon Europe “Satellites for Wilderness Inspection and Forest Threat Tracking” (SWIFTT) project.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Fire and burn are detection

Leveraging FIRMS data enables the identification of potential areas prone to fires. In this case, all pixels, encompassing probabilities ranging from 0 to 100, were utilized. This approach facilitated the creation of a Hotspots mask covering the territory of Ukraine. However, due to the low spatial resolution, this fire mask needs to be improved. The general scheme for creating a fire mask is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. The general scheme of creating a fire mask based on satellite data.

To augment the accuracy in pinpointing fire locations and mapping burned areas, we used the data extracted from Sentinel-2 satellite observations. To achieve this, we calculated the Normalized Burn Ratio (NBR) index, a metric enabling the identification of burned areas. This calculation was executed for each Sentinel-2 scene in our dataset:

$$NBR_{pre} = \frac{B8 - B12}{B8 - B12}, NBR_{post_i} = \frac{B8_i - B12_i}{B8_i - B12_i}. \quad (1)$$

The detection of fires was carried out by evaluating the ratio for each individual i -th image:

$$Fire_i = \frac{NBR_{pre} - NBR_{post_i}}{NBR_{pre} + 1.001} \geq threshold. \quad (2)$$

Having received a mask of burnt areas according to Sentinel-2 data and potential areas according to FIRMS data, we consider those pixels at the intersection of these two received data sets to be reliable.

To validate the generated fire mask, it is proposed to utilize temperature data derived from Landsat-8 and -9 satellites. Thermal infrared band (resampled from 100m to 30m) was used in this methodology. To identify fires, the maximum temperature for the studied area is identified, and temperatures with low values are filtered out. Subsequently, the validation of fires obtained from Sentinel-2 data is conducted, considering the constraints posed by limited available data due to cloud cover and the infrequent passes of Landsat satellites.

B. Fire Potential Index (FPI)

The Fire Potential Index (FPI) model was used to identify regions with the highest fire probability. The calculation was carried out according to the formula [15]:

$$FPI = (1 - FM_f) \cdot (1 - LR) \cdot 100 \quad (3)$$

where FM_f - represents fuel moisture, where fuel refers to the type of land cover, and Live Ratio (LR) is used to ascertain the ratio of living vegetation to dead vegetation. LR is determined using the following formula:

$$LR = \frac{RG_f \cdot LR_{mx}}{100} \quad (4)$$

The determination of Relative Greenness (RG_f), was carried out by leveraging vegetation indices, particularly NDVI, calculated from the rich dataset provided by MODIS satellite observations.

$$RG = \frac{ND_0 - ND_{mn}}{ND_{mx} - ND_{mn}} \cdot 100 \quad (5)$$

The equation involves the use of ND_0 , which represents the maximum NDVI value observed during the analyzed time period, as well as ND_{mn} and ND_{mx} , which denote the minimum and maximum NDVI values, respectively, recorded at the specific pixel's location over time. More details about the FPI calculation methodology can be found in the work [15].

To determine the type of land cover, a classification map for the territory of Ukraine with a spatial resolution of 10 m was used. The fire detection methodology described above using satellite data is implemented on the Google Earth Engine cloud platform.

IV. RESULTS

A. Fires hotspot according to FIRMS data

The Figure 2 illustrates the fire occurrences as identified through FIRMS data in the summer periods of 2021 (01.06.2021 – 30.08.2021) and 2022 (01.06.2022 – 30.08.2022). The geographic positioning of the discovered hotspots in 2022 reveals a notable concentration along conflict lines. Therefore, it motivated the inclusion of

additional research to ascertain potential causes of these fires in this study, particularly inspecting if weather conditions played a contributing role.

B. Burned areas of land according to Sentinel-2 data

As recorded between July 15-18, the total area burned was approximated at 104.2 thousand hectares, according data from Sentinel-2. The breakdown includes roughly 70 thousand hectares of cereal crops, 0.26 thousand hectares of rapeseed, 7.8 thousand hectares of summer crops, 25 thousand hectares of grassland, and 1.1 thousand hectares of forest. However, the estimates from Sentinel-2 may only present a lower limit as the presence of cloud cover at the time of satellite inspections might have influenced data accuracy. Given the fact that the average wheat yield in 2021 was 45.3 tons per hectare (as per the Ukrainian State Statistical Service), coupled with the fires occurring during the wheat and barley harvesting timeframe, it's estimated that potential losses for fires near the front line could amount to 3.17 million quintals, equivalent to 317 thousand tons, of grain.

Validation of our method for producing a fire mask from satellite data involved utilizing vector boundaries complemented by forest fires resulting from shelling. Specifically, we focused on the south region of Ukraine, with the Kherson region being the most affected during the month of May. The achieved overall accuracy for our method was 95.5%.

Fig. 2. Hotspots in Ukraine were identified using MODIS FIRMS data for a) 2021 and b) 2022 during the months of June to August.

C. FPI index

A Fire Potential Index was generated for the territory of Ukraine using satellite data and a land cover classification map, utilizing the Google Earth Engine cloud platform. The resulting index is a raster map with a spatial resolution of 250 m, providing values from 0 to 100 that represent the probability of fire occurrence. Figure 3 displays these maps, where blue values correspond to low values, and red values indicate high values [21].

The obtained results indicate that during the summer of 2021, fires were predominantly observed in the southern and eastern regions of Ukraine, in accordance with the Fire Potential Index. The occurrences of these fires could be attributed to weather conditions, as predicted by the Fire Potential Index, as well as human activities like field burning after harvest. In contrast, during 2022, there are evident discrepancies. However, in 2022, there were significant differences, with the Fire Potential Index suggesting potential fires primarily in the southern districts of Mykolaiv, Kherson, and Odesa regions. Nevertheless, the manifested fires seem to delineate a borderline, which implies they might be resulting from human actions such as the use of rockets and bombs.

a) 01.06-31.08.2021

b) 01.06-26.07.2022

Fig. 3. Fire Potential Index summer 2021 and 2022.

The results for 2021 reveal a correlation of 0.66 between the Fire Potential Index (FPI) and actual fires. Contributing factors to these fires encompassed meteorological conditions, aligning with the predictions of the Fire Potential Index, as

well as anthropogenic influences such as stubble burning in agricultural fields. Additionally, anthropogenic impact such as stubble burning in agricultural fields contributed to the fires. However, for 2022, the correlation coefficient is significantly lower, at 0.25, indicating a weaker connection between the Fire Potential Index and actual fires. When excluding oblasts where active hostilities are taking place, the correlation coefficient increases to 0.68. This observation supports the assessment, not just visually, but statistically, that fires in these conflict-torn regions are unlikely to be natural incidents but are largely due to military activities.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The results showcased in this article underscore the effectiveness of utilizing satellite data and land cover classification maps in a Fire Potential Index creation. This index, in turn, furnishes a probability estimate for the occurrence of fires across various regions of Ukraine. A Fire Potential Index was developed to predict areas at high risk for wildfires in Ukraine in 2021 and 2022. The 2021 map showed a correlation between high Fire Potential Index values and actual fire events, suggesting the index successfully identified high risk areas that year. However, the 2022 map did not correlate with real-world fires, indicating that weather conditions alone do not determine fire occurrence and other factors like human activity may play a role. The study also found that the majority of fires in 2022 occurred along the front line, indicating that they were human-caused by rockets and bombs, rather than weather conditions.

A potential road map for further research could involve leveraging Sentinel-1 radar data to address cloud cover limitations associated with Sentinel-2 optical data. Additionally, exploring the utilization of more contemporary indices for gauging fire danger could enhance the comprehensiveness and accuracy of the assessment. [22], [23].

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